

Asphalt Innovation Symposium 2025

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| SuPAR | Sustainable Pavements
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University
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Session 3B

Sustainable Dike Revetments: Indicators for Multi-Year Performance Tracking

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PRESENTATION OUTLINE

- **Introduction and Research Objective**
- **Materials and Methodology**
- **Results and Discussions**
 - ✓ *R-Index*
 - ✓ *Crossover Frequency and Crossover Modulus*
- **Conclusions and Recommendations**

INTRODUCTION AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

<https://expeditieaard e.blogspot.com/2011/12/netherlands-low-lying-country.html>

Vulnerable
to flooding

<https://gww-bouw.nl/en/waterworks/asphalting-and-machine-paving-under-a-slope/>

- Typical service life → 45 years; > 80% nearing end of service life
- Growing interest in exploring sustainable and circular solutions
- Urgent → alternative solutions sustain / enhance asphalt performance; meeting sustainability and circularity
- Recently, pilot dike sections constructed, alternative formulations → recycled contents, binder grades, filler proportions, and low-temperature production technologies
- Indicators/protocols at material scales lacking, reliable tracking ageing, support sustainable maintenance

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

Project I - Testing Alternative Field-Placed Dike Asphalt Formulations (Hot-Mix)

Project II - Testing Alternative Dike Asphalt Formulations in Laboratory (Warm-Mix)

Compares mastic rheological properties, right after construction and five years field exposure, three indicators → insights into multi-year asphalt performance in dikes

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MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

- Asphalt cores → six weeks after construction in year 0 and again in 5 years
- Bitumen and filler were extracted from field cores

7 mastic (binder and filler) formulations → same ratio as in field

1 reference mix

6 alternative formulations

8 mm diameter upper spindle (applies torque)

Bitumen film thickness of 2 mm

8 mm diameter lower plate

- Reclaimed asphalt (road and dike based) → 0 to 70%
- Filler-to-bitumen ratio → 0.48 to 2.30
- 3 binder grades → Pen 40/60, Pen 70/100, and Pen 160/220

- Frequency-sweep → 0 to 40 °C; 0.01 to 10 Hz
- Shift factors → William-Landel Ferry (WLF)
- Master curves (5 °C) → Christensen-Anderson-Marastean (CAM) model

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY (INDICATORS)

Rheological (R) index

- Shape parameter
- Prone bituminous materials are to ageing
- Higher R-index → increased ageing susceptibility

https://uwmarc.wisc.edu/files/binders2010/Continuous_Models_for_Characterizing_Linear_Viscoelastic_Behavior_of_Aspphalt_Binders_-_Anderson.pdf

Crossover modulus ($|G_c^*|$) & crossover frequency (f_c)

- $|G_c^*| \rightarrow$ storage and loss moduli intersect
- $f_c \rightarrow$ frequency corresponding to $|G_c^*|$ (phase angle, $\delta = 45^\circ$)

Lower $|G_c^*|$ and f_c
 \rightarrow increase in ageing

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS (R-INDEX)

- R-index → noticeable variation in different mastics (binder-filler systems) → binder grade, recycled content, and filler proportion
- **Mastic 2 → highest R-index values**
- At year 0; R-index 2, 6, and 7 > 1 (reference); reclaimed content (50 and 70%); higher filler contents and harder binder in 2, 6, and 7; competing effects; harder binder outweighed filler effects; resulting in higher R-index
- Mastics 4 and 5 → lowest R-index (years 0 and 5); high filler-to-binder ratio (reclaimed content 0 and 35%)
- After 5 years; R-index increased; statistically insignificant
- R-index, in general, captured ageing after 5 years, magnitude of change insignificant

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS (CROSSOVER PARAMETERS)

- In general, both $|G_c^*|$ and f_c reduced \rightarrow increase in ageing; except mastics 3 and 6 after five years
- **Mastic 1 (reference)** \rightarrow highest f_c both years \rightarrow softest binder and lowest filler-to-bitumen ratio; softer mastic
- Mastics 4 and 5 \rightarrow lower f_c and highest $|G_c^*|$ than mastic 1, harder binder and highest filler-to-bitumen, stiffer network dominated by high filler content

- Sections 2 and 6 \rightarrow similar composition, different ageing
- Statistical analysis \rightarrow **change in f_c significant and not in $|G_c^*|$** ; no consistent alteration in relaxation characteristics
- Lack of uniform trends in f_c and $|G_c^*|$; confirmed variations in reclaimed asphalt content, binder grade, and filler-to-bitumen proportions \rightarrow strong influence on change in viscoelastic behavior

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CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- Three rheological indicators → **complementary** insights into ageing
- In general, mastic level rheological indicators → **consistent aging**-related trends, however, **ability to differentiate** between aging levels **varied across three parameters**
- **Crossover frequency** → **statistically significant** change, while **R-index** and **crossover modulus** → **limited ageing** sensitivity after **5 years**
- Mastic level testing → changes in relaxation and **stiffness**, strongly influenced by **binder grade, filler-to-bitumen ratio, recycled content, and field exposure**
- Overall, while **recycled materials** offer circularity benefits, **proportion carefully managed** to avoid compromising durability; use **combination** of rheological **indicators** → reliable assessment of aging evolution
- Ongoing research → binder, mixture-level behavior and indicators that support long-term performance evaluation

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Thank you!

Questions, Comments, and Suggestions

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